

PROVIDING THE MANAGEMENT PROCESS WITH INFORMATION

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Annotation: this article provides complete information about information and its types, provision of information in the management process, description of information used in management, requirements for information quality.

Keywords: management, production, management, information, operational, economic, accounting, finance, supply, personnel, technological, design, marketing.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada axborot va uning turlari, boshqaruv jarayonida axborot bilan ta'minlash, boshqaruvda foydalaniladigan axborotlarning tavsiflanishi, axborot sifatiga qo'yiladigan talablar haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshqaruv, ishlab chiqarish, menejment, axborot, operativ, iqtisodiy, hisob, moliya, ta'minot, kadrlar bo'yicha, texnologik, konstruktorlik, marketing.

Аннотация: в данной статье приведены полные сведения об информации и ее видах, предоставление информации в процессе управления, описание информации, используемой в управлении, требования к качеству информации.

Ключевые слова: менеджмент, производство, управление, информация, оперативный, экономический, учет, финансы, снабжение, персонал, технологический, проектный, маркетинг.

The term "information" is a Latin word that means awareness, having information about an event or a person's activity. The information management system consists of a collection of information necessary for active influence in order to develop and improve it. It is impossible to manage without sufficient and accurate information. Production information is a method of communication between the controlling and controlled systems. The controlling system receives information about the state of production and its economic activity from the controlled system. The control system evaluates the activity of the controlled system based on the received information, issues instructions and orders for further improvement of control and sends them to the controlled system for execution. Information is a separate link in the management system. It has a number of unique features, which depend on covering all links and tasks of information management. Information is both a starting point and a result of the

activity of the management apparatus, as well as a condition for the existence of actions, a method of strengthening. As the volume of information increases, the demand for quality indicators of management information also increases.

There are the following types of information: statistical, operational, economic, accounting, financial, supply, personnel, technological, construction, marketing, social, and others. Depending on the source of origin, information is divided into external and internal types of information. External information consists of messages received from the external environment. These include information about the orders of higher organizations, plans and assignments, terms of sale of products. Internal information is formed and consumed in the enterprise or its management. At the enterprise level, they can include information about the execution of the plan by the workshops, material and technical support, product cost, personnel, and labor productivity. According to the direction, information is divided into initial and managerial (leadership) types of information.[1]

Management information is the result of decision-making based on initial information processing. Primary information always moves from lower levels of the management system to higher levels, while managerial information moves in the opposite direction. Production in market conditions requires a complex organization based on a systematic approach to the development and design of information systems. These requirements are met by an integrated data processing system. It is difficult to design it on the basis of modern calculators of various levels, human-machine system in all aspects. Management tasks are carried out through mutual cooperation, communication and information exchange between individuals and social groups. The concepts of information and communication are interconnected, but communication includes what is transmitted (information) and how it is transmitted. The activity of any manager is related to the following operations and activities:

- obtaining, checking and developing information;
- development and implementation of decisions;
- control their implementation and make corrections;
- systematization and storage of information on executed decisions.[2]

The information used in management is described as follows:

- according to the object of management;
- according to belonging to one or another management system;
- according to the form of transmission (verbal, verbal and non-verbal);
- according to time variability;
- according to the method of transmission;

- according to the order of transmission;
- as determined;
- according to the stages of the object's life cycle;
- according to the relationship of the management object to the subject.[3]

The main requirements for the quality of information are:

- timeliness;
- correctness; — sufficiency;
- reliability;
- addressability;
- multiple use;
- high speed of collection, development and transmission;
- possibility of coding;
- relevance.[4]

The information array is the arrangement of all types of information used by management agencies according to certain characteristics. It should provide the following: direct access of consumers to stored information, more complete satisfaction of their information needs, operative search and provision of information, and protection of data from corruption. Information flow is the movement of information from sources to consumers. The volume of information is a quantitative rate that is measured using conditional units (words, messages, characters, letters, sheets, etc.) and is used to determine the information content of management offices, to make decisions on management automation. The following should be ensured when designing document circulation:

- availability of necessary and sufficient information for making decisions in each document;
- rationalization of information flows by eliminating documents and indicators contained in them;
 - reducing the direction of receiving documents from the source to the consumer;
- effective control over the terms of execution of documents;
- unification of forms of documents.[5]

It should be noted that the global information superhighway of the Internet and the local network of corporations will fundamentally change the technology of collecting and processing information for managers, and most importantly, it will provide equal customers with remote communication without vertical bureaucracy, that is, partnership forms horizontal temporary structures. To

diagnose the quality of information systems work and analyze it, there is a concept of information quality, which is usually evaluated by the following parameters: correctness, non-contradiction, accuracy, speed, relevance (relevance). Non-verbal information, that is, information sent by the sender without using words, also plays a very important role.

In deed, They form the basis of non-verbal communication. Gestures, facial expressions, intonations are an important part of business communication. Sometimes these tools (they are called non-verbal) and words can say a lot more. The main types of non-verbal information are:

- physical condition of a person (height, weight, hair color, body structure, etc.);
- movements of the body (gestures, posture, touching, facial expression, eye movements, etc.);
- speech (intonations, literacy, sound, speed of speech, etc.);
- environment (illumination, noise, illumination, structure, furniture, etc.);
- use of the environment (habits of behavior, communication distance, etc.);
- time (coming early, staying late, making oneself wait, etc.).

References:

1. Bekmurodov A., G'afurov U., Tukhliyev B. the world effective economic policy of Uzbekistan in the conditions of financial and economic crisis. Study guide. - T.: TD1U. - P. 84
2. Kasimova D. Roofing. Marketing strategy i apply. "Case Study" method to the business education system in Uzbekistan application. Collection of cases. - T.: Akademia, 2006. - P. 158
3. Mirsaidov M. S. Fundamentals of Entrepreneurship. Textbook. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2005. – P.75
4. Tulyaganova D., Akaitdinova M. Sociology and psychology of management. Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2004. – P. 18
5. Kasimova D. Management theory. Study guide. - T.: Science and technology, 2009. – P. 35

